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The Curved Interfacial Crack Analysis between Foam and Composite Materials under Antiplane Shear Loading

H. –J. Chun¹ and S. H. Park²

¹ *School of Electrical and Mechanical Engineering, Yonsei University 134, Shinchon-dong, Seodaemun-gu, Seoul, 120-749, Korea : hjchun@yonsei.ac.kr*

² *Department of Mechanical Engineering, Yonsei University 134, Shinchon-dong, Seodaemun-gu, Seoul, 120-749, Korea : dasom38@yonsei.ac.kr*

SUMMARY: The curved interfacial crack between viscoelastic foam and composite materials was investigated with shear stresses applied at infinity or constant surface traction acting along the interfacial crack. Kelvin-Maxwell model was used to represent viscoelastic characteristics of foam. Laplace transform was applied to treat the viscoelastic characteristics of foam in the analysis. The problem in the curved crack was reduced to a Hilbert problem and a closed-form asymptotic solution was derived to incorporate the effect of curvature. The stress intensity factors in the vicinity of the interfacial crack tip were predicted by considering both anisotropic and viscoelastic properties of composite and foam materials, respectively. In the case of shear stresses applied at infinity, the ratio of stress intensity factors between curved and linear interfaces increases remarkably with increasing the curvature of interface in comparison with constant surface traction. The stress intensity factor near the curved interfacial crack tip increases with increasing curvature and the ratio of stiffness coefficients of foam and composite materials.

KEYWORD : Interfacial Crack, Viscoelasticity, Foam, Antiplane Loading

INTRODUCTION

The sandwich structures composed of foam core and composite skins are available for various industrial applications due to the advantages of high flexural strength and impact resistance. However, foam core sandwich structures have the possibility of the presence of crack at the interface between foam and composite materials. Furthermore, during the fabrication process, the structures have good possibility of the occurrence of initial defect at the interface between foam and composite materials especially when the shape of structures is complicated such as curved shape.

Up to this time, the researches of stress field and stress intensity factor near the interfacial crack tip in various materials have been accomplished [1-3]. E. Smith studied the problem involving the extension of non-planar cracks contained within an inhomogeneous solid deforming in an antiplane strain mode [4]. R. C. Chang investigated the stress intensity factor

near the interfacial crack between viscoelastic materials with considering the viscoelasticity and presented the result that the stress intensity factor increased with time [5]. S. Yang *et al.* investigated the dissimilar interfacial circular crack in cylindrically anisotropic composites under antiplane shear[6].

In this paper, the curved interfacial crack between viscoelastic foam and composite materials was investigated with shear stresses applied at infinity or constant surface traction acting along the interfacial crack. Kelvin-Maxwell model was used to represent the viscoelasticity of foam. The stress intensity factors were predicted by considering two cases of shear stresses applied at infinity without surface traction acting along the interfacial crack and constant surface traction acting along the interfacial crack without shear stresses applied at infinity. The effects of curvature and elastic properties of foam and composite materials on the stress intensity factors near the curved interfacial crack were investigated and discussed.

BASIC FORMULATION

The geometry and coordinates of the analytical model are shown in Fig.1. In this analytical model, a curved crack is subtended with an angle 2α at the center of curvature and is located in the interface between foam and composite materials. S^- and S^+ are considered as foam and composite materials, respectively.

Fig. 1 Geometry and coordinates of curved interfacial crack between foam and composites

From the analytical model in Fig. 1, the problem can be assumed to be 2-dimensional and independent of z -axis, then consequently the displacements in the r - and q - directions disappear. The constitutive equations of the model are expressed as

$$\mathbf{t}_{rz} = C_{44} \mathbf{g}_{rz} = C_{44} \frac{\partial w}{\partial r}, \quad \mathbf{t}_{qz} = C_{55} \mathbf{g}_{qz} = C_{55} \frac{1}{r} \frac{\partial w}{\partial q} \quad (1)$$

where $w(r, q)$, \mathbf{t}_{ij} , \mathbf{g}_{ij} and C_{kl} are the displacement in the z -direction, stress components, strain components and the stiffness coefficient, respectively.

The equilibrium equation can be expressed as

$$C_{44} \left(\frac{\partial^2 w}{\partial r^2} + \frac{1}{r} \frac{\partial w}{\partial r} \right) + C_{55} \left(\frac{1}{r^2} \frac{\partial^2 w}{\partial q^2} \right) = 0 \quad (2)$$

The general solution of Eq. (2) is similar to Lekhnitskii's complex variable stress potentials[7] and can be expressed as

$$w(r, \mathbf{q}) = [W(z_c) + \overline{W(z_c)}] \quad (3)$$

where argument z_c is defined as

$$z_c = a \left(\frac{a}{r} \right)^{iz} e^{iq} \quad (4)$$

where a is a characteristic length designated as the radius of the circular curve and coefficients \mathbf{z} are the roots of the following characteristic equation.

$$C_{44} \mathbf{z}^2 + C_{55} = 0 \quad (5)$$

Stress components can be expressed using $w(r, \mathbf{q})$ as

$$\mathbf{t}_{rz} = \frac{2}{r} \operatorname{Re} \left[\sqrt{C_{44} C_{55}} z_c \frac{dW(z_c)}{dz_c} \right], \quad \mathbf{t}_{\theta z} = \frac{2}{r} \operatorname{Re} \left[\mathbf{z} \sqrt{C_{44} C_{55}} z_c \frac{dW(z_c)}{dz_c} \right] \quad (6)$$

It is convenient to introduce a function

$$\Phi(z_c) = \sqrt{C_{44} C_{55}} z_c \frac{dW(z_c)}{dz_c} \quad (7)$$

So that the stress and strain components can be simply expressed as

$$\mathbf{t}_{rz} = \frac{1}{r} [\Phi(z_c) + \overline{\Phi(z_c)}], \quad \mathbf{t}_{\theta z} = \frac{1}{r} [\mathbf{z} \Phi(z_c) + \overline{\mathbf{z} \Phi(z_c)}], \quad \frac{\partial w}{\partial \mathbf{q}} = \frac{i}{\mathbf{m}} [\Phi(z_c) - \overline{\Phi(z_c)}] \quad (8)$$

where $\mathbf{m} = \sqrt{C_{44} C_{55}}$

Fig. 2 The variation of fiber orientation of uniaxial laminate

Fig. 2 shows the schematic drawing for the variation of fiber orientation of uniaxial laminate. The angle between \mathbf{q} -axis and fiber orientation is assigned to \mathbf{v} and transformed stiffness coefficients (C'_{ij}) are given by

$$\begin{aligned} C'_{44} &= C_{44} \cos^2 \mathbf{v} + C_{66} \sin^2 \mathbf{v} \\ C'_{55} &= (C_{11} + C_{33} - 2C_{13} - 2C_{55}) \cos^2 \mathbf{v} \sin^2 \mathbf{v} + C_{55} (\cos^4 \mathbf{v} + \sin^4 \mathbf{v}) \end{aligned} \quad (9)$$

ANALYTICAL MODEL OF FOAM MATERIALS

Foam has the viscoelastic features that the mechanical properties vary with time. In this paper Kelvin-Maxwell model is presented in order to simulate the viscoelastic behavior of foam. Laplace transform is used to treat the viscoelastic characteristics of foam in the analysis. The stiffness coefficients of foam can be expressed as a function of time such as

$$C_{ijkl}(t) = C_{ijkl}^1 e^{-t/l} + C_{ijkl}^0 \quad (10)$$

where $C_{ijkl}(t)$, l , t , C_{ijkl}^1 and C_{ijkl}^0 are the stiffness coefficient of foam considering viscoelasticity, the relaxation time, the elapsed time, coefficients related to relaxation time and stiffness coefficient of foam at $t = \infty$, respectively.

The stress-strain relations of foam can be expressed as

$$\mathbf{s}_{ij}(t) = C_{ijkl}^0 \mathbf{e}_{kl} + \int_0^t C_{ijkl}(t-x) \mathbf{e}_{kl}(\mathbf{x}) d\mathbf{x} \quad (11)$$

Applying the characteristic equation (5) to Laplace transform, then Eq. (5) is expressed as

$$\hat{C}_{44} \hat{z} + \hat{C}_5 = 0 \quad (12)$$

where the notation ‘ $\hat{}$ ’ denotes the functions applied to Laplace transform.

In the same way, Eqs. (7) and (8) are applied to Laplace transform, then

$$\hat{\Phi}(z_c) = \sqrt{\hat{C}_{44} \hat{C}_{55} z_c} \frac{d\hat{W}(z_c)}{dz_c} \quad (13)$$

$$\mathbf{t}_{rz} = \frac{1}{r} [\hat{\Phi}(z_c) + \overline{\hat{\Phi}(z_c)}], \quad \mathbf{t}_{rz} = \frac{1}{r} [\hat{\Phi}(z_c) + \overline{\hat{\Phi}(z_c)}], \quad \frac{\partial \hat{W}}{\partial \mathbf{q}} = \frac{i}{\hat{\mathbf{m}}} [\hat{\Phi}(z_c) - \overline{\hat{\Phi}(z_c)}] \quad (14)$$

where $\hat{\mathbf{m}} = \sqrt{\hat{C}_{44} \hat{C}_{55}}$

BOUNDARY CONDITIONS

Considering the interface between foam and composite materials, the boundary conditions on the crack surface are written as

$$\hat{\Phi}_1(z) + \overline{\hat{\Phi}_1(z)} = \mathbf{t}(z), \quad \hat{\Phi}_2(z) + \overline{\hat{\Phi}_2(z)} = \mathbf{t}(z) \quad \text{on } z = ae^{iq}, \quad |q| < a \quad (15)$$

where subscripts denote the internal and external materials, respectively, and $\mathbf{t}(z)$ is traction which is applied to each crack surface. The traction is applied to interfacial crack surface with the opposite direction to each other. The boundary conditions on the interface except the crack is given by continuation condition as follows

$$\frac{1}{\hat{\mathbf{m}}} [\hat{\Phi}_1(z) - \overline{\hat{\Phi}_1(z)}] = \frac{1}{\hat{\mathbf{m}}} [\hat{\Phi}_2(z) - \overline{\hat{\Phi}_2(z)}] \quad \text{on } z = ae^{iq}, \quad |q| > a \quad (16)$$

$$\hat{\Phi}_1(z) + \overline{\hat{\Phi}_1(z)} = \hat{\Phi}_2(z) + \overline{\hat{\Phi}_2(z)}$$

INTERFACIAL CRACK UNDER UNIFORM SHEAR AT INFINITY

When the analytical model is applied to the uniform shear stresses at infinity without the traction along the interfacial crack ($r \rightarrow \infty, \mathbf{t}_x^\infty = \mathbf{t}_y^\infty = \mathbf{t}_{rz}$), it is possible to define the two new functions from Eq. (15) which are analytic functions in the whole plane cut along the interfacial crack except the origin and infinity as follows

$$\begin{aligned} \hat{\Psi}(z) &= \hat{\Phi}_1(z) & z \in S^+, & & \hat{\Psi}(z) &= -\overline{\hat{\Phi}_1(z)} & z \in S^- \\ \hat{\Theta}(z) &= -\overline{\hat{\Phi}_2(z)} & & & \hat{\Theta}(z) &= \hat{\Phi}_2(z) & \end{aligned} \quad (17)$$

From Eq. (17) the boundary condition in Eq. (16) is written as

$$\left[\frac{\hat{\Psi}^+(z) - \hat{\Theta}^+(z)}{\hat{\mathbf{m}}_1} - \frac{\hat{\Psi}^-(z) - \hat{\Theta}^-(z)}{\hat{\mathbf{m}}_2} \right] + \left[\frac{\hat{\Psi}^-(z) - \hat{\Theta}^-(z)}{\hat{\mathbf{m}}_1} - \frac{\hat{\Psi}^+(z) - \hat{\Theta}^+(z)}{\hat{\mathbf{m}}_2} \right] = 0 \quad \text{on } z = ae^{iq}, |q| > a \quad (18)$$

$$\left[\hat{\Psi}^+(z) + \hat{\Theta}^+(z) \right] - \left[\hat{\Psi}^-(z) - \hat{\Theta}^-(z) \right] = 0$$

where superscripts denote the limiting values of functions approaching from S^+ and S^- to the interfacial crack surfaces respectively. Eq. (18) is a pair of Hilbert problem[8] and the functions $\Psi(z)$ and $\Theta(z)$ can be determined from the solution of Eq. (18) as follows

$$\frac{\hat{\Psi}(z) - \hat{\Theta}(z)}{\hat{\mathbf{m}}_1} - \frac{\hat{\Psi}(z) + \hat{\Theta}(z)}{\hat{\mathbf{m}}_2} = \hat{\mathbf{c}}_0(z)\hat{R}(z), \quad \hat{\Psi}(z) + \hat{\Theta}(z) = \hat{P}(z) \quad (19)$$

$$\text{where } \hat{P}(z) = \sum_{k=-1}^1 D_k z^k, \quad \hat{R}(z) = \sum_{k=-1}^2 C_k z^k, \quad \hat{\mathbf{c}}_0(z) = (z - ae^{ia})^{-1/2} (z - ae^{-ia})^{-1/2}$$

Replacing the argument z of functions $\hat{\Psi}(z)$ and $\hat{\Theta}(z)$ by z_c . From Eqs. (19) and (8), the stresses can be expressed in the following forms

$$\mathbf{t}_{rz}^{(1)} = \frac{2}{r} \frac{\hat{\mathbf{m}}_1 \hat{\mathbf{m}}_2}{\hat{\mathbf{m}}_1 + \hat{\mathbf{m}}_2} \text{Re} \left[\frac{\hat{P}(z_c)}{\hat{\mathbf{m}}_2} + \hat{\mathbf{c}}_0(z_c) \hat{R}(z_c) \right], \quad \mathbf{t}_{rz}^{(2)} = \frac{2}{r} \frac{\hat{\mathbf{m}}_1 \hat{\mathbf{m}}_2}{\hat{\mathbf{m}}_1 + \hat{\mathbf{m}}_2} \text{Re} \left[\frac{\hat{P}(z_c)}{\hat{\mathbf{m}}_1} - \hat{\mathbf{c}}_0(z_c) \hat{R}(z_c) \right] \quad (20)$$

$$\mathbf{t}_{z_c}^{(1)} = \frac{2}{r} \frac{\hat{\mathbf{m}}_1 \hat{\mathbf{m}}_2}{\hat{\mathbf{m}}_1 + \hat{\mathbf{m}}_2} \text{Re} \left\{ \mathbf{z}_1 \left[\frac{\hat{P}(z_c)}{\hat{\mathbf{m}}_2} + \hat{\mathbf{c}}_0(z_c) \hat{R}(z_c) \right] \right\}, \quad \mathbf{t}_{z_c}^{(2)} = \frac{2}{r} \frac{\hat{\mathbf{m}}_1 \hat{\mathbf{m}}_2}{\hat{\mathbf{m}}_1 + \hat{\mathbf{m}}_2} \text{Re} \left\{ \mathbf{z}_2 \left[\frac{\hat{P}(z_c)}{\hat{\mathbf{m}}_1} - \hat{\mathbf{c}}_0(z_c) \hat{R}(z_c) \right] \right\}$$

From the boundary conditions and Eq. (20), the coefficients of the functions $\hat{P}(z_c)$, $\hat{R}(z_c)$ and $\hat{\mathbf{c}}_0(z_c)$ can be determined. Expanding $\hat{\Psi}(z_c)$ for a small distance r from crack tips and keeping terms up to the order of $o(\sqrt{r})$, the first three-term asymptotic expansions of crack-tip stress field [6] are

$$\mathbf{t}_{g_i}^{(k)} = \sum_{i=1}^3 A_i \mathbf{r}^{s_i} \mathbf{t}_{g_i}^{(i)}(\mathbf{j}) \quad (21)$$

$$\text{where } \mathbf{g} = r, \mathbf{q}, \quad k = 1, 2, \quad s_1 = -\frac{1}{2}, \quad s_2 = 0, \quad s_3 = \frac{1}{2}$$

The stress intensity factor applied to the Laplace transform can be determined by the leading term of Eq. (21) which approximate to the exact solution [6]. Introducing the stress intensity factor (\hat{K}_{III}) applied to the Laplace transform by the leading term, Eq. (21) can be written as

$$\mathbf{t}_{rz}^{(k)} = \frac{\hat{K}_{III}}{\sqrt{2pr}} \text{Re} \left[\frac{1}{\sqrt{\cos \mathbf{j} + \mathbf{z}_k \sin \mathbf{j}}} \right], \quad \mathbf{t}_{z_c}^{(k)} = \frac{\hat{K}_{III}}{\sqrt{2pr}} \text{Re} \left[\frac{\mathbf{z}_k}{\sqrt{\cos \mathbf{j} + \mathbf{z}_k \sin \mathbf{j}}} \right] \quad (22)$$

$$\text{where } \hat{K}_{III} = \frac{2\hat{\mathbf{m}}_1}{\hat{\mathbf{m}}_1 + \hat{\mathbf{m}}_2} \sqrt{ap \sin \mathbf{a}} \left(\mathbf{t}_x^\infty \cos \frac{\mathbf{a}}{2} \pm \mathbf{t}_y^\infty \sin \frac{\mathbf{a}}{2} \right)$$

Taking inverse Laplace transform, the stress intensity factor is expressed as

$$K_{III} = 2[S - He^{-Q(t-t_0)}] \sqrt{ap \sin \mathbf{a}} \left(\mathbf{t}_0 \cos \mathbf{b} \cos \frac{\mathbf{a}}{2} \pm \mathbf{t}_0 \sin \mathbf{b} \sin \frac{\mathbf{a}}{2} \right) \quad (23)$$

$$\text{where } S = \frac{\sqrt{C_{44}C_{55}}}{\sqrt{C_{44}C_{55} + G_f^0}}, \quad Q = \frac{1}{I} \frac{(\sqrt{C_{44}C_{55} + G_f^0})}{\sqrt{C_{44}C_{55} + G_f^1 + G_f^0}}, \quad H = \frac{G_f^1 \sqrt{C_{44}C_{55}}}{\sqrt{C_{44}C_{55} + G_f^1 + G_f^0}} \frac{1}{\sqrt{C_{44}C_{55} + G_f^1 + G_f^0}}$$

where \mathbf{b} , G_f^1 and G_f^0 are the angle between \mathbf{t}_0 and x-axis, coefficient related to relaxation time(I) and stiffness coefficient of foam at $t = \infty$, respectively. The stress

intensity factor of the rectilinear interfacial crack can be determined as

$$\lim_{a \rightarrow \infty} \sum_{aa=const} K_{III} = K_{III}^L = 2[S - He^{-Q(t-t_0)}] \sqrt{2a\mathbf{a}}(\mathbf{t}_0 \cos \mathbf{b}) \quad (24)$$

INTERFACIAL CRACK UNDER CONSTANT SURFACE TRACTION

When the analytical model is applied to the constant surface traction along the curved interfacial crack ($\mathbf{t}(z) = -\mathbf{t}_0$) without uniform stresses at infinity, the two new functions can be defined from Eq. (22) in a similar way to Eq. (17) as follows

$$\begin{aligned} \hat{\Psi}(z) &= \frac{1}{\hat{\mathbf{m}}} \hat{\Phi}_1(z) + \frac{1}{\hat{\mathbf{m}}} \overline{\hat{\Phi}_2(z)}, & \hat{\Theta}(z) &= \hat{\Phi}_1(z) - \overline{\hat{\Phi}_2(z)} & z \in S^+ \\ \hat{\Psi}(z) &= \frac{1}{\hat{\mathbf{m}}} \hat{\Phi}_2(z) + \frac{1}{\hat{\mathbf{m}}} \overline{\hat{\Phi}_1(z)}, & \hat{\Theta}(z) &= \hat{\Phi}_2(z) - \overline{\hat{\Phi}_1(z)} & z \in S^- \end{aligned} \quad (25)$$

From Eq. (25) the boundary conditions in Eq. (15) are written as

$$\hat{\Psi}^+(z) + \hat{\Psi}^-(z) = \frac{\hat{\mathbf{m}} + \hat{\mathbf{m}}}{\hat{\mathbf{m}}\hat{\mathbf{m}}} a \mathbf{t}(z), \quad \hat{\Theta}^+(z) - \hat{\Theta}^-(z) = 0 \quad \text{on } z = ae^{i\mathbf{q}}, \quad |\mathbf{q}| < \mathbf{a} \quad (26)$$

Equation (26) is a pair of Hilbert problem[10] and the functions $\Psi(z)$ and $\Theta(z)$ can be determined from the solution of Eq. (26) as follows

$$\hat{\Psi}(z) = -\frac{1}{2} \frac{\hat{\mathbf{m}} + \hat{\mathbf{m}}}{\hat{\mathbf{m}}\hat{\mathbf{m}}} a \mathbf{t}_0 [1 + (a \cos \mathbf{a} - z) \hat{\mathbf{c}}_0(z)] + \hat{\mathbf{c}}_0(z) \hat{R}(z), \quad \hat{\Theta}(z) = \hat{P}(z) \quad (27)$$

Replacing the argument z of functions $\hat{\Psi}(z)$ and $\hat{\Theta}(z)$ by z_c and from Eqs. (25) and (8) the stresses can be expressed in the following forms

$$\begin{aligned} \mathbf{t}_{r_c}^{(1)} &= \frac{2}{r} \frac{\hat{\mathbf{m}}\hat{\mathbf{m}}}{\hat{\mathbf{m}} + \hat{\mathbf{m}}} \operatorname{Re} \left[\hat{\Psi}(z_c) + \frac{\hat{\Theta}(z_c)}{\hat{\mathbf{m}}} \right], & \mathbf{t}_{r_c}^{(2)} &= \frac{2}{r} \frac{\hat{\mathbf{m}}\hat{\mathbf{m}}}{\hat{\mathbf{m}} + \hat{\mathbf{m}}} \operatorname{Re} \left[\hat{\Psi}(z_c) + \frac{\hat{\Theta}(z_c)}{\hat{\mathbf{m}}} \right] \\ \mathbf{t}_{z_c}^{(1)} &= \frac{2}{r} \frac{\hat{\mathbf{m}}\hat{\mathbf{m}}}{\hat{\mathbf{m}} + \hat{\mathbf{m}}} \operatorname{Re} \left\{ \mathbf{z}_1 \left[\hat{\Psi}(z_c) + \frac{\hat{\Theta}(z_c)}{\hat{\mathbf{m}}} \right] \right\}, & \mathbf{t}_{z_c}^{(2)} &= \frac{2}{r} \frac{\hat{\mathbf{m}}\hat{\mathbf{m}}}{\hat{\mathbf{m}} + \hat{\mathbf{m}}} \operatorname{Re} \left\{ \mathbf{z}_2 \left[\hat{\Psi}(z_c) + \frac{\hat{\Theta}(z_c)}{\hat{\mathbf{m}}} \right] \right\} \end{aligned} \quad (28)$$

From the boundary conditions and Eq. (28), the coefficients of the functions $\hat{P}(z_c)$, $\hat{R}(z_c)$ and $\hat{\mathbf{c}}_0(z_c)$ can be determined. Expanding $\hat{\Psi}(z_c)$ for a small distance r from crack tips and keeping terms up to the order of $o(\sqrt{r})$, the first three-term asymptotic expansions of crack-tip stress field [6] are

$$\mathbf{t}_{z_c}^{(k)} = \sum_{i=1}^3 A_i \mathbf{r}^i \mathbf{t}_{z_c}^{(i)}(\mathbf{j}) \quad (29)$$

The stress intensity factor applied to the Laplace transform can be determined by the leading term of Eq. (29) which approximate to the exact solution[6]. Introducing the stress intensity factor (\hat{K}_{III}) applied to the Laplace transform by the leading term, Eq. (29) can be written as

$$\mathbf{t}_{r_c}^{(k)} = \frac{\hat{K}_{III}}{\sqrt{2\mathbf{p}\mathbf{r}}} \operatorname{Re} \left[\frac{1}{\sqrt{\cos \mathbf{j} + \mathbf{z}_k \sin \mathbf{j}}} \right], \quad \mathbf{t}_{z_c}^{(k)} = \frac{\hat{K}_{III}}{\sqrt{2\mathbf{p}\mathbf{r}}} \operatorname{Re} \left[\frac{\mathbf{z}_k}{\sqrt{\cos \mathbf{j} + \mathbf{z}_k \sin \mathbf{j}}} \right] \quad (30)$$

$$\text{where } \hat{K}_{III} = K_{III} = \mathbf{t}_0 \sqrt{2a\mathbf{p} \tan \frac{\mathbf{a}}{2}} \quad (31)$$

From Eq. (31) it can be observed that the stress intensity factor is not affected by the material properties. Considering both the inner and outer materials are isotropic, Eq. (30) coincides with that given by Smith [6]. The stress intensity factor of the rectilinear interface

crack becomes

$$\sum_{\substack{a \rightarrow \infty \\ aa = \text{const}}} K_{III} = K_{III}^L = t_0 \sqrt{\frac{aa}{2}} \quad (32)$$

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

Fig. 3 shows the stress intensity factor as a function of the curvature for constant surface traction along interfacial crack and prescribed shear stresses at infinity. In the case of constant surface traction, the stress intensity factor is not much affected by the curvature of interface. On the other hand, when shear stresses are applied at infinity, the stress intensity factor increases with increasing the curvature of interface. Fig. 4 shows the ratio of the stress intensity factors between curved and linear interfaces as a function of the curvature of interface between foam and composite materials with constant traction along interfacial crack surface and shear stresses at infinity. In the case of constant surface traction, it is found that the ratio of the stress intensity factor between curved and linear interface increases monotonically as the curvature of interface increases. In case of shear stresses at infinity, however, it is observed that the ratio of the stress intensity factors between curved and linear interfaces increases remarkably with increasing the curvature of interface in comparison with that with constant surface traction. The stress intensity factor (K_{III}) as a function of the curvature of interface between foam and composite materials under uniform stresses at infinity is shown in Fig. 5. It can be observed that the stress intensity factor increases with increasing curvature as well as the ratio of stiffness coefficients between foam and composite

Fig. 3 K_{III}/t_0 as a function of the curvature of interface between foam and composite materials with constant surface traction along interfacial crack and shear stresses at infinity ($C_{55} : G_f = 1:1.4$, crack size = const.)

Fig. 4 The ratio of the stress intensity factors between curved and linear interface as a function of the curvature of interface with constant surface traction along interfacial crack and shear stresses at infinity

materials. Fig. 6 shows that the stress intensity factor increases with increasing the ratio of stiffness coefficients between foam and composite materials for a fixed curvature, and eventually converges to a specific value.

Fig. 5 $K_{III}(t)/t_0$ as a function of the curvature of curved interface between foam and composite materials with various ratios of C_{55}/G_f ($G_f^0 : C_{44} = 1 : 2.2, t_x^\infty = t_y^\infty = t_0$)

Fig. 6 K_{III}/t_0 as a function of the ratio of stiffness coefficients (C_{55}/G_f) between foam and composite materials with a fixed curvature (crack size : radius(a) = 1:15, $t_x^\infty = t_y^\infty = t_0$)

Fig. 7 K_{III}/t_0 as a function of the normalized time with various values of I
 ($G_f^0 : C_{44} : C_{55} : G_f^1 = 10 : 22 : 40 : 1/I$, crack size : radius(a) = 1:15, $t_x^\infty = t_y^\infty = t_0$)

Fig. 7 illustrates the stress intensity factor as a function of the normalized time for various relaxation time (I). The stress intensity factor increases with time and finally converges to a specific value. The reason for the increase of stress intensity factor with time is that the stiffness coefficient of viscoelastic foam decreases with time and the difference in the stiffness coefficients between foam and composite materials increases. The increasing rate of the stress intensity factor depends on the value of relaxation time. The stress intensity factor for $I=0.5$ converges rapidly to a specific value with time in comparison with that for $I=2$.

Fig. 8 The variation of stiffness coefficients with fiber orientation

Fig. 9 K_{III}/t_0 as a function of the fiber orientation with various ratio of stiffness coefficients ($C_{55} : G_f$) between foam and composite materials
(crack size : radius(a) = 1:15, $t_x^\infty = t_y^\infty = t_0$)

Fig. 8 shows the variation of stiffness coefficients with fiber orientation. The stiffness coefficient (C_{44}) in the r - z plane changes rapidly with fiber orientation and reaches the maximum when fiber orientation is 45° . However, the stiffness coefficient (C_{55}) in the θ - z plane changes monotonically. The variation of stress intensity factor with fiber orientation is shown in Fig. 9. It shows that the stress intensity factor reaches the maximum when the fiber orientation is 45° . These results in Fig. 9 agree well with the former results that the stress intensity factor increases with increasing the difference in stiffness coefficients between foam and composites, considering that the stiffness coefficient (C_{44}) in composites under antiplane shear loading is at its maximum when fiber orientation is 45° . It can be also observed that the effect of fiber orientation on the stress intensity factor decreases with increasing the difference in the stiffness coefficients between foam and composite materials

CONCLUSIONS

The curved interfacial crack between viscoelastic foam and composite materials was investigated with shear stresses applied at infinity and constant surface traction acting along the interfacial crack. In the case of constant surface traction, the stress intensity factor was not affected by the material properties, and the ratio of the stress intensity factors between curved and linear interfaces increased monotonically as the curvature of interface increased. In the case of shear stresses at infinity, the stress intensity factor was governed by the material properties and increased with increasing curvature as well as the ratio of stiffness coefficients of foam and composite materials. Furthermore, the ratio of the stress intensity factors between curved and linear interfaces increases remarkably with increasing the curvature of interface in comparison with that with constant surface traction.

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REFERENCES

1. M. L. Williams, The Stresses around a Fault or Crack in Dissimilar Media, *Bull. Seismol. Soc. Amer.*, 1959, vol. 49, pp. 199-204
2. C. Hwu, Fracture Parameters for the Orthotropic Bimaterial Interface Cracks, *Engineering Fracture Mechanics*, 1993, vol. 45, pp. 89-97
3. T. C. Ting, Explicit Solution and Invariance of the Singularities at an Interface Crack in Anisotropic Composites, *Int. J. Solids Structures.*, 1986, vol. 22, pp. 965-983
4. E. Smith, The Extension of Circular-Arc Cracks in Anti-Plane Strain Deformation, *Int. J. Engng Sci.*, 1969, Vol. 7, pp. 973-991
5. R. C. Chang, Viscoelastic Composite with a Cracked Layer under Anti-plane Shear,

Theoretical and Applied Fracture Mechanics, 1997, vol. 27, pp. 53-62

6. S. Yang, and F. G. Yuan, Interfacial Circular Crack in Cylindrically Anisotropic Composites under Antiplane Shear, *Int. J. Solids Structures.*, 1995, vol. 32, pp. 3603-3628.
7. S. G. Lekhnitskii, Theory of Elasticity of an Anisotropic Elastic Body, *Holden-Day*, San Francisco, 1963
8. N. I. Muskhelishvili, Some Basic Problems of the Mathematical Theory of Elasticity, Fourth Edition, *P. Noordhoff*, 1963
9. Ronald F. Gibson, Principles of Composite Material Mechanics, *McGraw-Hill*, New York, 1994, pp. 270-330